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Executive Summary

The present deliverable, ‘**D9.3 – Implementation guidance and guidelines**’, part of Work Package 9 ‘Ethical and Legal Framework’ (WP9) of the In Silico World project, offers **guidelines on the ethical legal aspects of In Silico Trials** for researchers and end users. The report builds on the previous reports ‘D9.1 – Legal and Ethical Inventory’ and ‘D9.2 – In-depth analysis of legal and ethical requirements’, which assessed the core pieces of legislation and ethical principles relevant to In Silico Trials. The guidelines concern the areas of legislation already identified in D9.1 and D9.2, i.e. privacy, data protection and data governance, medical devices and medical products, artificial intelligence, and ethics. Short and descriptive recommendations are provided for each of them, as recapitulated in the following.

Guidelines to In Silico Trials researchers and end-users

Privacy, Data Protection and Data Governance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Respect the principles of data processing</i> 2. <i>Assess data protection roles</i> 3. <i>Be mindful of the legal bases for data processing activities</i> 4. <i>Be security aware</i> 5. <i>Keep ready for upcoming regulations</i>
Medical Devices and Medicinal Products	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. <i>Document the research process</i> 7. <i>Consult Good Simulation Practice recommendations</i>
Artificial Intelligence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. <i>Reflect upon the ethical aspects entailed by the use of AI</i> 9. <i>Keep ready for upcoming AI requirements</i>
Ethics	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. <i>Consider the principles of Biomedical Ethics</i> 11. <i>Perform responsible research</i> 12. <i>Use Generative AI responsibly</i>

This report is part of the second **evaluative step** of WP9 legal and ethical research (D9.2 and D9.3). Unitedly with D9.1, this deliverable will support policy recommendations to EU legislators and policymakers, to be provided in the final deliverable of WP9 (‘D9.4 – Validation and recommendations for lawmakers and policymakers’).

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

This deliverable is based on the former Deliverable ‘D9.1 – Ethical and legal inventory of in silico trials’ and ‘D9.2 – In-depth analysis of legal and ethical requirements’, which identified and described the relevant **legal and ethical framework** for In Silico Trials. In light of the identified framework, this report offers **guidelines** to In Silico Trials researchers and end-users to help them navigate the said framework. With a set of twelve “golden rules”, the report aims to support In Silico Trials stakeholders towards an ethically and legally sound implementation of the ethical and legal requirements identified throughout the project.

1.2. Document outline

To achieve the above objective, this deliverable contains twelve main recommendations (also called “golden rules”) and it is divided into five main sections, mirroring the main categorisations delineated in D9.1 and D9.2. Section 2, ‘**Privacy, Data Protection and Data Governance**’, contains five main recommendations (*1.1 Respect the principles of data processing; 1.2 Assess data protection roles; 1.3 Be mindful of the legal bases for data processing; 1.4 Be security aware; 1.5 Be ready for upcoming regulations*) aiming to raise awareness on the importance of privacy, data protection and data governance aspects in In Silico Trials. Section 3, ‘**Medical Devices and Medicinal Products**’ contains two main rules (*3.1 Document the research process; 3.2 Consult Good Simulation Practice recommendations*) focusing on the documentation requirements and good practices for In Silico Trials research. Section 4, ‘**Artificial Intelligence**’, suggests that in some instances In Silico Trials tools may entail the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI). In that case, two rules are suggested: *4.1 Reflect upon the ethical aspects entailed by the use of AI*, and *4.2 Keep ready for upcoming AI legal requirements*. Section 5, ‘**Ethics**’, complements the part of legal recommendations. The main rules provided therein suggests to *Consider the principles of biomedical ethics* (section 5.1), *Perform responsible research* (section 5.2), and *Use Generative AI responsibly* (section 5.3). All these sections distil the formerly identified ethical and legal requirements in D9.1 and D9.2.¹ Section 6 concludes.

2. Privacy, Data Protection and Data Governance

In Silico Trials may entail processing personal data from its early stages to more advanced phases. Medical researchers, engineers, developers, and other stakeholders, such as patient representatives and regulatory authorities, should consider **privacy, data protection, and data governance legal requirements**. D9.1 and D9.2 provided an extensive overview of the most relevant pieces of legislation, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR),² the Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation³, the Open Data Directive,⁴ the

¹ Those interested in a more in-depth analysis should refer to these two. See Elisabetta Biasin, ‘In Silico World D9.1 Legal and Ethical Inventory’ <<https://zenodo.org/record/7104079>> accessed 10 January 2023; Biasin, Elisabetta, ‘In Silico World D9.2 In-Depth Analysis of Legal and Ethical Requirements’ <<https://zenodo.org/record/7991233>> accessed 31 May 2023.

² Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) [2016] OJ L119/1 (GDPR).

³ Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union [2018] OJ L303/59 (FFNPDR).

⁴ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information [2019] OJ 172/56 (Open Data Directive).

Data Governance Act (DGA),⁵ the Data Act,⁶ the European Union’s (EU) treaties and conventions⁷, the relevant guidelines and guidance documentation.⁸ At the same time, the former deliverables reported on the evolving framework of data legislation – which has changed rapidly in the last five years. This report summarises in five “golden rules” the core aspects of data laws that developers and end-users should retain from their activities for In Silico Trials (sections 2.1, 2.2., 2.3, 2.4). It also suggests considering possible requirements that could stem from forthcoming legislation, such as the EHDS, Data Act and Data Governance Act regulations (section 2.5).

2.1. Respect the principles of data processing

The **principles of data processing** are the essence of data protection legal requirements.⁹ These are lawfulness, fairness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimisation; accuracy; storage limitation; integrity and confidentiality (as represented in Figure 1).

Figure 1 Principles of data processing in the GDPR

The **principle of lawfulness, fairness, and transparency** requires that personal data be processed lawfully, fairly, and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject.¹⁰ “**Lawfully**” means that every planned data processing activity should have a legal basis (see section 2.3). “**Fairly**” means considering how the processing may impact individuals and how any adverse effect may be felt and that personal data are processed in a way that individuals reasonably expect. “**Transparency**” entails clarity over the controller’s personal data processing activities.

- **Example:** Hospital patients’ data are used for In Silico Trials scientific research. To ensure transparency in the processing of their data, they must be informed of the processing from the moment of their

⁵ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act) [2022] OJ L152/1.

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act) [2023] OJ L.

⁷ Including the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), the Council of Europe Convention 2018 (Convention 108), the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and on the functioning of the European Union (TFEU), the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union; see D9.1 for the full list.

⁸ Including the OECD Guidelines on the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data, the Council of Europe Recommendation on the protection of health-related data, European Data Protection Board’s (EDPB) guidelines, European Data Protection Supervisor’s (EDPS) opinions; see D9.1 for the full list.

⁹ For a detailed analysis of these principles, see Biasin, Elisabetta (n 1) 10.

¹⁰ GDPR, art 5(1)(a).

enrollment. For example, privacy notices should let them know their data may be used for scientific research and what legal basis is used for the further processing of their data.

Purpose limitation means data shall be collected for specified, explicit, legitimate purposes. It requires the controller to define the purpose of data processing before it starts. Any further processing shall be done in a manner that is compatible with the initial purposes.¹¹ When further processing is deemed “not incompatible with the initial purpose,” there is no need for a new legal basis.¹² **Scientific research** is, in principle, not considered incompatible with the initial purpose of the processing therefore, a new legal basis should not be required.¹³ However, exceptions could apply as EU Member States have the faculty to introduce further limitations, including consent requirements, for the further processing health data (for further considerations, see also section 2.3).¹⁴

- Example: In Silico Trials researchers want to use data from a former project in a new scientific research project. Following the principle of purpose limitation, they should evaluate the legal basis (preferably with the support of a legal team), and if the scientific research exception may apply.¹⁵

Data minimisation is the principle of data processing requiring that personal data are ‘adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary about the purposes for which are processed’.¹⁶ Researchers and end users should strictly limit the use of data in processing activities to what is necessary to achieve a legitimate purpose. They should identify the minimum amount of personal data without exceeding what is needed to fulfil the identified purpose. As much as possible, researchers should try to fulfil the processing activity through anonymisation or other technical measures that can reduce the risks of patient identification (e.g. pseudonymisation, use of synthetic data, etc.).

- Example: Processing a patient’s health data to build an In Silico Trial model would, in principle, not require access to their banking detail data.

The principle of **accuracy** requires data to be accurate and kept up to date when necessary. If the controller becomes aware that personal data is inaccurate, they should take (when possible) reasonable steps and ensure that data are either erased or rectified.¹⁷

¹¹ GDPR, art 5(1)(b). To understand the difference between “primary processing” and “further processing”, let us consider the following example. A hospital collects patients’ data for their treatments and the same data are reused for scientific research. The data collection for treatments can be considered as primary processing, and the use of the same data by the hospital researchers as further processing.

¹² GDPR, rec 50. The compatibility for the new processing activity has to be assessed on a case-by-case basis, having regard on a variety of factors. These include the relationship between the initial and the secondary purposes, the context in which the data are collected and the reasonable expectations of the data subjects for their further use, the nature of the personal data and the impact of the further processing on the and the safeguards adopted by the controller to ensure a fair processing. See further Article 29 Working Party, ‘Opinion 03/2013 on Purpose Limitation’ <https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2013/wp203_en.pdf>.

¹³ GDPR, Article 5(1)(b).

¹⁴ GDPR, art 9(4).

¹⁵ For an overview, see Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency., *Assessment of the EU Member States’ Rules on Health Data in the Light of GDPR*. (Publications Office 2021) <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2818/546193>> accessed 5 March 2024. For a detailed illustration of the Italian legal requirements on the processing of health data in biomedical research, see Paola Aurucci, *Il trattamento dei dati personali nella ricerca biomedica: problematiche etico-giuridiche* (Prima edizione, Università degli studi di Torino : Edizioni scientifiche italiane 2023).

¹⁶ GDPR, art 5(1)(c).

¹⁷ GDPR, art 5(d).

- **Example:** In AI-based medical research, if personal health data are inaccurate, the inferences (such as predictive risks scores) of the AI tool can be incorrect. Researchers using personal health data within *in silico* tools should put in place mechanisms to check the accuracy of collected data and record the source of those data.

The **storage limitation** principle requires that data must be kept in a form that permits the identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed.¹⁸ This principle, in practice, implies that controllers should establish data retention periods determining the duration of data storage, or periodical reviews on the data held, possibly entailing data erasure, anonymisation or pseudonymisation. This principle foresees a specific **exception** for data processed in the context of **scientific research**.¹⁹ However, this exception should not be taken as a blank check for unlimited storage of personal data, nor should it be a pretext for other private purposes.²⁰

- **Example:** In Silico Trials researchers, when making use of personal data for their research, should consider whether their research facilities apply data retention policies. At the end of their research project, they should consider whether and when techniques such as anonymisation or pseudonymisation could be used. In case of doubt, their Data Protection Officer (DPO) should be able to provide appropriate indications.²¹

Accountability is the overarching principle of data protection law. It requires controllers and processors to take responsibility for their processing activities and demonstrate compliance with data protection requirements. The controller shall have a *proactive role* in adhering with data protection requirements through technical and organisational measures while being able to *demonstrate compliance* with those requirements.

Finally, it is important to underline that **scientific research is a high-risk data processing activity**. According to EU data protection bodies, scientific research often entails the processing and sharing of data of sensitive type of personal data.²² As such, high-risk data processing activities require the consideration of additional safeguards. Safeguards include respect for professional ethics standards, the execution of a data protection impact assessment (DPIA), data minimisation through pseudonymisation, and (unless it would impair research) anonymisation.²³ In light of this, In Silico Trials researchers should consider and coordinate internally with internal data protection experts to assess the appropriate safeguards for processing personal data in scientific research.

2.2. Assess data protection roles

Processing personal data entails observing legal requirements, which are, in turn, directed to specific entities or stakeholders. For this reason, the **assessment of data protection roles** is essential when performing scientific research for In Silico Trials.

¹⁸ GDPR, art 5(e).

¹⁹ The GDPR establishes such an exemption, as storage is essential to facilitate the verification of research results – even when the research project is over. Furthermore, it facilitates the further processing of personal data, in case they want to engage in new research projects. For more remarks, see Rossana Ducato, ‘Data Protection, Scientific Research, and the Role of Information’ (2020) 37 Computer Law & Security Review 105412.

²⁰ European Data Protection Supervisor, ‘A Preliminary Opinion on Data Protection and Scientific Research’ <https://edps.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publication/20-01-06_opinion_research_en.pdf>.

²¹ GDPR, art 37.

²² European Data Protection Supervisor (n 20) 24.

²³ *ibid.*

The GDPR foresees different data protection roles, assuming different responsibilities depending on how they contribute to the data processing activities. The most relevant roles in the GDPR are the data subject, data controller and the data processor.

The **data subject** is the identified or identifiable natural person whose data is processed by the data controller or the processor. In scientific research, patients are usually considered data subjects (inasmuch the processed data in the project relate to them). The **data controller** is the natural or legal person that determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data,²⁴ while the **data processor** is the natural or legal person which processes the personal data on behalf of the controller.²⁵ The data controller determines the ‘how’ and ‘why’ of the processing, while the data processor carries out the processing based on the instructions provided by the controller.²⁶ In some cases, more entities determine the purposes and means of the processing (a situation called “**joint controllership**”).²⁷

A **scientific research project usually involves several entities**, including healthcare providers, research institutions such as universities, health technology providers or developers (e.g. medical device manufacturers) but also sub-processors and contractors (such as IT service providers, cloud providers). Sometimes determining the data protection roles can be a complex task. We provide below some examples of data protection role allocation to facilitate the orientation of researchers and end users within In Silico Trials research:²⁸

- **Controllership:** A PhD researcher with their supervisor determine the objectives of their nationally funded, person-specific doctoral research to be carried out at their university. The researcher collects personal health data directly from research participants. The University is likely to be the controller for the activities entailed by this specific doctoral project.
- **Joint controllership:** A researcher and their team are involved in an international research project. The partners define together the research design and processing activities. The partners are likely to qualify as joint controllers.
- **Processorship:** University researchers, along with the University hospital process health data in the context of pharmaceutical industry funded research. Likely, the pharmaceutical company, as sponsor of the clinical trial, will act as data controller. The University and the University hospital are likely to be data processors.

Further complexities: It is important to be aware that entities could assume a data protection role for some processing activities, and a different role for other ones. Scientific research activities may, thus, entail different processing purposes:

- **Example:** several research institutions are participating in a common research project.²⁹ They may be joint controllers for providing data into a platform used to perform research. For that activity, they

²⁴ GDPR, art 4(7).

²⁵ GDPR, art 4(8).

²⁶ EDPB, ‘Guidelines 07/2020 on the Concepts of Controller and Processor in the GDPR’ <https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/edpb/files/consultation/edpb_guidelines_202007_controllerprocessor_en.pdf> accessed 11 March 2020.

²⁷ GDPR, art 26. Joint participation can happen through a common decision undertaken by different entities, or they could result from converging decisions, if they complement one with the other. In this case, joint controllers mutually define their respective responsibilities for compliance through a joint controllership arrangement.

²⁸ See also: Ghent University, ‘GDPR: What Are the Different Roles and Responsibilities According to the GDPR? | (Re)Search Tips’ <<https://onderzoektips.ugent.be/en/tips/00001789/>> accessed 21 March 2024.

²⁹ The example originates from the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR. See EDPB (n 26) 21.

may be joint controllers. Nevertheless, if the same entities perform other processing activities outside the same platform for other purposes, they may be separate controllers (or even processors) depending on the nature of the further processing activity.

As seen in the examples above, data processing circumstances may be heterogeneous. Depending on the specificities of the scientific project, role allocation may assume more complex settings than the above. As a general good practice, In Silico Trials researchers should seek advice on role allocation from their institution's team specialised in internal data protection or the DPO.

2.3. Be mindful of the legal bases for data processing

Performing research and using In Silico Tools in healthcare research settings may entail the use of personal data.³⁰ Once evaluated whether there is a processing of personal data – as in some cases, such as anonymised data, the GDPR does not apply – In Silico Trials researchers and end users are called to consider on which basis the processing is taking place.

Carrying out health data processing in In Silico Trials means performing a **personal data processing activity**. As seen in the data processing principles above, every personal data processing activity must be lawful, i.e. it shall be carried out further to an appropriate legal basis. The legal bases for health data processing require considering two key articles of the GDPR: Article 6 and Article 9. Article 6 sets out the legal requirements for the **lawfulness of the processing**, and it usually applies to 'common' personal data. According to it, the legal bases for processing personal data processing are:³¹

- **Consent** of the data subject;
- **Performance of a contract** with the data subject;
- The necessity of compliance with a **legal obligation**;
- Protection of the **vital interests** of the data subject or another natural person;
- Performance of a **task** carried out in the **public interest** or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller;
- **Legitimate interest** of the controller or of third parties.³²

In the case of scientific research, however, the processing activities will likely concern not only personal data but also **special categories of personal data**. Special categories of personal data are those categories considered more sensitive and, thus, worthy of a higher level of protection.³³ According to the GDPR, special categories of personal data include 'data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic data, biometric data to uniquely identify a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation'.³⁴

³⁰ When processing data within the context of In Silico Trials, the first step is to understand whether the data processed are to be considered 'personal data'. As also outlined in other In Silico World legal reports, pseudonymous data are still personal data, while anonymised data, in principle, should not be considered as personal data. For synthetic data, it is crucial to be cautious since, at this point in time, both literature and data protection stakeholders are discussing the nature of (non-)personal data. Further remarks summarising the data protection intricacies of synthetic data are provided under section 'Focus: synthetic data' of D9.2. See Biasin, Elisabetta (n 1) 14.

³¹ GDPR, art 6.

³² For an in-depth analysis carried out previously in the project, see Biasin, Elisabetta (n 1) 16.

³³ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party, 'Advice Paper on Special Categories of Data ("sensitive Data")'.

³⁴ GDPR, art 9.

Most importantly, In Silico Trials research may entail the processing of **data concerning health**.³⁵ Examples of data concerning health are information from medical tests, genetic data and biological samples, information about a disease, disability, or disease risk, information about medical history, clinical treatment, or information about the physiological or biomedical state of an individual.³⁶

The **processing of special categories of personal data** is, in principle, prohibited by the GDPR. Any processing of personal health data will have to fall under the explicit and close-numbered exceptions enumerated under Article 9(2) GDPR. Therefore, the above legal bases are insufficient for conducting In Silico Trials research with personal health data. They shall be combined with the legal grounds of Article 9(2) GDPR.³⁷

The most relevant conditions for the processing of health data within In Silico Trials research are as follows:

- **Explicit consent** of the patient;
- the processing is necessary to protect the **vital interests** of a data subject (or another person), and the data subject is physically or legally incapable of giving consent;
- the processing is necessary for reasons of **substantial public interest** on the basis of the Union State law;
- the processing is necessary for the purposes of **preventive or occupational medicine**;
- the processing is necessary for **reasons of public interest in the area of public health**, such as protecting against serious cross-border threats to health or ensuring high standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices;
- the processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, **scientific** or historical **research purposes** or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) GDPR.
 - * The GDPR leaves the possibility to Member States to introduce further requirements to these existing legal bases.³⁸

Existing guidance and literature are not particularly keen on considering **consent** as the most appropriate legal basis for the primary use of health data. The other legal bases may be more suitable in that respect. It is also of core importance to **not confuse data protection consent with informed consent in clinical trials**. The first (GDPR consent) is one of the possible legal bases for the processing of personal data, while the second (informed consent) is the ethical-legal requirement for the involvement of human participants in scientific research.

Furthermore, the legal basis must be **considered for every research project** carried out by the same research team. Having a set of personal data for a specific research project does not in fact automatically entail that the same personal health data can also be used in a new health project. This issue is commonly known as **further processing** of personal health data (or “secondary use”).³⁹ Unfortunately, the legal aspects concerning further processing in research entail several uncertainties for healthcare stakeholders.⁴⁰ The takeaway rule is, therefore, that researchers must be aware that any further processing of personal data may require the

³⁵ Former project reports have more extensively explained the meaning and scope of ‘special categories of personal data’ and ‘data concerning health’. See Biasin, Elisabetta (n 1) 2.

³⁶ GDPR, rec 35.

³⁷ For a more in-depth analysis of legal bases under Article 9 GDPR, see Biasin, Elisabetta (n 1).

³⁸ A comprehensive EU-wide study has mapped the EU Member States’ rules on health data in the light of GDPR. See Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency. (n 15).

³⁹ “Secondary use” is the wording adopted in the most recent data governance regulations. For an overview thereof see *infra*, section 2.5 ‘Keep ready for upcoming regulations’.

⁴⁰ For an accurate scrutiny, see among others Regina Becker and others, ‘Secondary Use of Personal Health Data: When Is It “Further Processing” Under the GDPR, and What Are the Implications for Data Controllers?’ (2022) 30 European Journal of Health Law 129.

additional evaluation of a new legal basis. While in many cases the further processing can be presumed **compatible** with the initial one, it might not happen 100% of the times. Therefore, it is always best to consider the case with appropriate legal support.

2.4. Be security aware

In the past, healthcare **cybersecurity** was not considered by organisations as important as it is today. However, after the COVID-19 pandemic, it became clear to the broader public that healthcare infrastructures and patients' data are core targets for malicious actors.⁴¹ Security is a factor that concerns the many layers of data processing activities, and entails different responsibilities in the cybersecurity chain.⁴²

Engineers and end users shall consider **data security practices** in their daily activities. For In Silico Trials developers, security starts from gathering the research data and making sure these are stored in a secure manner. Security remains important during modelling and research experimentation, and even after the conduction of the research project itself. When researchers have processed sensitive or health-related data, it is important that they are kept securely (if a storage period after the initial processing is foreseen by the controller).

Data security means also that research data shall retain their **integrity** characteristics, especially when these are planned to be further used and shared in future projects. Moreover, security is also important to consider when AI tools are used in the processing activities. Most recent cyber-attacks may entail "data poisoning", which may cause malfunctioning of AI prediction/classification tools, or inaccuracy in their results.⁴³

Poor data security practices can lead to **personal data breaches**, exposing patients' data to several risks. Data breaches have different forms. According to the GDPR, personal data breaches may lead to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, or unauthorised disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored or otherwise processed.⁴⁴ The GDPR definition includes the case of malicious actors accessing on-purpose IT systems of a healthcare or research entity. At the same time, the GDPR refers to cases where personal data breaches are caused accidentally, e.g. by human error and a poor knowledge of cybersecurity best practices.⁴⁵

Personal data breaches may concern **confidentiality** when data is accessed without authorisation or by accident. Data breaches may also concern **integrity** – if personal data are altered (accidentally or without authorisation) – or **availability**, where there is a loss of access or destruction of personal data.⁴⁶ Usually, organisations provide instructions concerning data protection and data security. Researchers and engineers should carefully consider them.

Security requirements stem from the existing **General Data Protection Regulation**, as part of the integrity and confidentiality principle.⁴⁷ However, these may also stem from other cybersecurity regulations such as the **NIS**

⁴¹ Elisabetta Biasin, 'Cybersecurity in Sanità, Dalla Nis al Gdpr: Punti Deboli e Vantaggi' (*Agenda Digitale*, 2020) <<https://www.agendadigitale.eu/sanita/cybersecurity-in-sanita-dalla-nis-al-gdpr-punti-deboli-e-vantaggi/>>.

⁴² Erik Kamenjasevic and Danaja Fabcic Povse, 'A Data Protection Perspective on Training in the mHealth Sector' in Giuseppe Andreoni, Paolo Perego and Enrico Frumento (eds), *m_Health Current and Future Applications* (Springer International Publishing 2019) <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-030-02182-5_5> accessed 23 February 2024.

⁴³ For a more detailed analysis of cyber-attacks examples with AI, see Elisabetta Biasin and others, 'Cybersecurity of AI Medical Devices: Risks, Legislation, and Challenges' (Edward Elgar 2023).

⁴⁴ GDPR, art 4(12).

⁴⁵ Kamenjasevic and Povse (n 42).

⁴⁶ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party, 'Guidelines on Personal Data Breach Notification under Regulation 2016/679' 7 <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/item-detail.cfm?item_id=612052> accessed 3 November 2020.

⁴⁷ GDPR, art 5(1)(f); see also GDPR, arts 32-34.

Directive for healthcare providers (hospitals).⁴⁸ In the future, more requirements may be introduced by the NIS2 Directive (in its future implementation by EU Member States), which will also apply to medical device manufacturers and other entities in the health sector.⁴⁹ In Silico Trials researchers and end users shall have an interest in considering security requirements of these regulations, especially when developing *in silico* tools qualifying as medical devices.⁵⁰

2.5. Keep ready for upcoming regulations

In recent years, the European legal framework on data governance has changed dramatically, in general, and with regard to the healthcare domain. The growing interest in the **free flow of data** led European policy-makers to consider **data governance** as a new regulatory domain. As of 2018, the EU produced a series of documentation to concretely push the policy objectives of creating a package of measures for establishing common data spaces in the EU. Since then, there have been several proposed data reforms.⁵¹ The most relevant updates for Silico Trials researchers and end-users are the Data Governance Act, the Data Act and the proposed European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation.⁵² This section describes them briefly, and recommends In Silico Trials stakeholders considering their forthcoming requirements – more in-depth detailed in D9.1 and D9.2 – as new compliance items for future research projects.

The **Data Governance Act** will be relevant for In Silico Trials researchers and end users as they provide the possibility and mechanisms for acquiring data useful to conduct scientific research. The regulation was put forward in 2020 by the European Commission and was approved in May 2022. It aims to facilitate the use of certain categories of data held by public-sector bodies and increase trust in data sharing across different stakeholders. The regulation incorporates the conditions and mechanisms allowing the **re-use of certain categories of data** and establishes a framework for providing data intermediation services by data intermediation service providers or data cooperatives. It establishes secure processing environments and

⁴⁸ Directive (EU) 2016/1148 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 July 2016 concerning measures for a high common level of security of network and information systems across the Union [2016] OJ 194/1. For an overview of the main NIS Directive cybersecurity-related requirements applicable in the health context, see Elisabetta Biasin and Erik Kamenjasevic, 'Cybersecurity of Medical Devices: Regulatory Challenges in the European Union' in Carmel Shachar and others (eds), *The Future of Medical Device Regulation: Innovation and Protection* (Cambridge University Press 2022) <<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/future-of-medical-device-regulation/cybersecurity-of-medical-devices/AC01289C2DB05E44D0D98A9E66666562>>.

⁴⁹ Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive) [2022] OJ 194/1. For an overview on how the NIS2 Directive impacts the healthcare sector, see Elisabetta Biasin and Erik Kamenjašević, 'Cybersecurity of Medical Devices: New Challenges Arising from the AI Act and NIS 2 Directive Proposals' (2022) 3 *International Cybersecurity Law Review* 163; Elisabetta Biasin, 'The NIS2 Proposal: Which Regulatory Challenges for Healthcare Cybersecurity?' (*CITIP blog*, 4 May 2021) <<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/the-nis2-proposal-which-regulatory-challenges-for-healthcare-cybersecurity/>> accessed 7 June 2022.

⁵⁰ The EU Medical Device Coordination Group has provided guidance on how to ensure cybersecurity of medical devices. See Medical Device Coordination Group, 'MDCG 2019-16 Guidance on Cybersecurity for Medical Devices' (2019) <https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-01/md_cybersecurity_en.pdf>.

⁵¹ Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of Regions "Towards a Common European Data Space" COM(2018) 232 Final (Towards a Common European Data Space)'; European Commission, 'Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. A European Strategy for Data'.

⁵² Commission, 'Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Health Data Space' COM(2022) 197 final (European Health Data Space proposal).

introduces provisions for the voluntary sharing of data on the basis of consent of data subjects or data holders' permission – also known as **data altruism**.

The **Data Act** is another EU regulation relevant for In Silico Trials researchers and end users for using data in scientific research. It was proposed by the European Commission in February 2022 and it was approved in November 2023. Similarly to the Data Governance Act, the Data Act is a horizontal regulation applying across different sectors, including healthcare. It concerns, among other things, **access and re-use of data** in the context of business-to-business, business-to-consumer and business-to-government data sharing.

The proposed **European Health Data Space** (EHDS) Regulation promises to modify the existing legal framework on health data sharing as we know it.⁵³ In Silico Trials researchers and end users will be certainly impacted by the EHDS Regulation on their activities concerning data sharing in research, from collection, to processing, to further processing and providing them to another requesting entity. The EHDS proposal was published in May 2022. At the moment of writing, EU institutions have reached a political agreement.⁵⁴

The forthcoming EHDS regulation has many objectives. It aims to: i) strengthening individual rights in relation to the availability and control of their health data; ii) set rules and mechanisms for the **primary and secondary use of health data**; iii) set rules for the placing on the market of **electronic health records** systems and wellness devices; and iv) setting cross-border infrastructures enabling the primary and secondary use of electronic health data. The regulation will have a wider scope than the GDPR as it will concern personal and non-personal data. The requirements foreseen in this regulation are copious. It will establish new entities and authorities related to data sharing, such as health data access bodies, the digital health authorities and the European Health Data Space Board. Of most relevance for In Silico Trials researchers and end users will be the new rules setting the modalities and conditions for the allowed primary and secondary use of electronic health data.

In conclusion, the DGA, EHDS and Data Act will impact In Silico Trials researchers and end users. Their requirements were already described in former In Silico World reports (D9.1 and D9.2). Ultimately, In Silico Trials researchers and end users should prepare and be **ready to comply** with their new requirements.

3. Medical Devices and Medicinal Products

In Silico Trials researchers may be involved in the execution of activities to develop solutions to target different specialities, diseases, and medical products. Depending on the specificities of each research project, Silico Trials solutions may entail legal considerations from a product regulation perspective.⁵⁵

Medical device legal requirements may become relevant, for example, when In Silico researchers develop software tools to predict a disease's prognosis or treatment (such as software analysing a patient's response to a medicinal product). In that case, the tool may fall under the definition of medical device software. Digital Health Twins are another example of which an In Silico Tool may likely fall under the medical device software category.⁵⁶ In Silico Trials researchers may also develop solutions to target medicinal products. Therefore, **medicinal products and pharmaceutical legislation** are another relevant areas for In Silico Trials tools. It could be the case, for example, of an *in silico* tool that is developed to help simulate the human immune system's response to exposure to certain pathogens and predict the outcome of a new medication or vaccine. Such a

⁵³ These were extensively analysed in D9.1 and D9.2, to which this report refers for further details.

⁵⁴ Council of the European Union, 'European Health Data Space: Council and Parliament Strike Deal' (15 March 2024) <<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/03/15/european-health-data-space-council-and-parliament-strike-provisional-deal/>> accessed 25 March 2024.

⁵⁵ See Biasin, 'In Silico World D9.1 Legal and Ethical Inventory' (n 1) 29.

⁵⁶ Cristina Curreli, 'Review of Current Regulatory Pathways in Europe and the USA to Certify DTHs and MDDT/DDT' (The regulatory barriers to in silico trials (In Silico World workshop), Catania, 14/03).

tool may be considered, in regulatory terms, as a “new methodology” within the evaluation of medicinal products.

D9.1 and D9.2 enlisted the most relevant pieces of legislation applicable to In Silico Trials from a medical product perspective. These include laws on **clinical trials**,⁵⁷ **medical devices**⁵⁸ or **advanced therapeutic medicinal products** (ATMPs)⁵⁹. The two sections below distil two main recommendations in light of the identified relevant legal requirements in D9.1 and D9.2 (*3.1 Document the research process*), having regard also to the latest advancements in the field of good simulation practices (*3.2 Consult Good simulation practices recommendations*).

3.1.Document the research process

Both the existing medical device and clinical trials regulations demand **meticulous documentation** and proof of informed consent to uphold ethical standards and legal requirements.

If an *in silico* tool falls under the definition of **medical device** (most likely, “medical device software”), In Silico Trials researchers are called to consider the relevant requirements of the Medical Device Regulation (MDR)⁶⁰ or the In Vitro Medical Device Regulation (IVDR)^{61,62}. Medical device regulations foresee a series of requirements called general safety and performance requirements.⁶³ These requirements mandate manufacturers, among others, to maintain **technical documentation**. Technical documentation is particularly important as it facilitates the submission and regulatory evaluation of the medical device. According to the MDR, the documentation shall include, among other, the device description and specification, information about design and manufacturing, details on the information to be supplied to the end user, and design and manufacturing information. It shall contain information to demonstrate conformity with medical device laws’ safety and performance requirements, including a justification, validation and verification of the solutions adopted to meet those requirements. Demonstration of conformity will have to describe the methods used, the harmonised standards or solutions applied. For product verification and validation, the documentation shall contain the results and critical analyses of all verifications and validation tests or studies taken. For example, for pre-clinical and clinical data, results of tests, such as engineering, laboratory or simulated use and evaluation of published literature applicable to the devices should be provided, but also information regarding test design, complete test or study protocols, methods of data analysis, data summaries and data conclusions. Specific information is then required for **software verification and validation**, that shall describe

⁵⁷ Including, for instance, the Declaration of Helsinki, the Declaration of Taipei, the Clinical Trials Directive, the Good Clinical Practice Directive, the Clinical Trials Regulation. See D9.1 for the full inventory of the relevant legislation.

⁵⁸ Including the Medical Device Regulation and In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Device Regulation. For more details, see D9.1.

⁵⁹ Regulation (EC) No 1394/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 November 2007 on advanced therapy medicinal products and amending Directive 2001/83/EC and Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 [2007] OJ L324/121 (ATMP Regulation).

⁶⁰ See Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC [2017] OJ L117/1 (MDR).

⁶¹ Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU [2017] OJ L117/176 (IVDR).

⁶² Therefore, the preliminary aspect to consider is to whether an In Silico Trial tool may fall under the definition of medical device software. See Medical Device Coordination Group, ‘MDCG 2019-11 Guidance on Qualification and Classification of Software in Regulation (EU) 2017/745 - MDR and Regulation (EU) 2017/746 - IVDR’.

⁶³ Among the many aspects, medical device laws require manufacturers to have risk management and quality management systems in place, as well as conducting a conformity assessment procedure before putting the device on the market. For a more in-depth overview, see Biasin, ‘In Silico World D9.1 Legal and Ethical Inventory’ (n 1) 32.

the software design and development process and evidence of the validation of the software as used in the finished device.

Medicinal products and pharmaceutical legislation are the second relevant area identified for *in silico* tools. As seen above, an *in silico* solution could be considered in regulatory terms as a “new methodology” for evaluating medicinal products. In that case, the necessary step for this solution/methodology is to be formally considered *acceptable* by the competent authority.⁶⁴ In the European Union, the **European Medicines Agency** (EMA) is involved in such evaluation. The most relevant procedure before the EMA for this purpose is the so-called **qualification process**.⁶⁵ A qualification process can lead either to a **qualification opinion** concerning the acceptability of a specific use of a proposed method (such as a novel methodology) in a research and development context or it can lead to a **qualification advice**, which will concern the future protocols and methods for further method development towards qualification.⁶⁶ In both cases, documentation is essential. The most recent guidance provided by the EMA suggests appropriately setting up documentation to offer insights about the reliability, repeatability, accuracy and clinical applicability of the methodology subject to the qualification process.⁶⁷ **Documentation** will have to be accompanied by other elements, such as research question elements (including the concept of interest, context of use, identification of a clinically meaningful change, benefits of using digital measures instead of the existing methods) or additional requirements related to compliance (such as the MDR/IVDR, where applicable, and data protection laws).

As seen above, In Silico Trials researchers developing *in silico* tools may have to consider requirements from medical devices or medicinal products legislation. Therefore, for regulatory purposes, it is important for them to document their processes thoroughly. Finally, if they carry out scientific research involving human participants, they must include in their documentation procedures the modalities to collect and track participants’ **informed consent**.

3.2. Consult Good Simulation Practice recommendations

As known by researchers and end users of In Silico Trials, the practice of In Silico Trials is still far from being established.⁶⁸ Given the lack of existing regulatory pathways and relevant good practices, the In Silico World project hosted a Community of Practice (ISW_CoP) with the aim of developing a consensus report of experts working in In Silico Trials. In March 2024, the book “**Toward Good Simulation Practice**” was published by the participants of the said community of practice.⁶⁹ The document summarises the good practices for researchers in Silico Trials regarding the use of simulation data and evidence in the regulatory process of medical products.

⁶⁴ This is a simplified explanation. For a more punctual analysis, see Biasin, Elisabetta (n 1) 40.

⁶⁵ D9.2 contains a detailed description of this procedure. *ibid* 39.

⁶⁶ *Ibid*.

⁶⁷ See European Medicines Agency, ‘Questions and Answers: Qualification of Digital Technology-Based Methodologies to Support Approval of Medicinal Products’ (2020); Francesca Cerreta and others, ‘Digital Technologies for Medicines: Shaping a Framework for Success’ (2020) 19 *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery* 573.

⁶⁸ In Silico World, ‘Good Simulation Practice’ (*In Silico World*) <<https://insilico.world/community/good-simulation-practice/>> accessed 28 March 2024.

⁶⁹ See Marco Viceconti and Luca Emili (eds), *Toward Good Simulation Practice: Best Practices for the Use of Computational Modelling and Simulation in the Regulatory Process of Biomedical Products* (Springer Nature Switzerland 2024) <<https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-031-48284-7>> accessed 28 March 2024. The document was published with the support of the Virtual Physiological Human Institute (VPHi) and Avicenna Alliance (AA).

It is set to provide a ‘list of the best practices to use computer simulation to assess the safety and efficacy of medical products’.⁷⁰

As there is no *ad hoc* regulatory guidance on In Silico Trials, researchers may benefit from a set of community-agreed practices to develop and use *in silico* solutions tools. The Towards Good Simulation Practice book may offer relevant recommendations to In Silico Trials and researchers for the development and regulatory submission of In Silico Trial solutions.

4. Artificial Intelligence

In Silico Trials may entail, in certain circumstances, the **use of Artificial Intelligence**.⁷¹ The legal framework concerning AI in the EU – in general and in the context of healthcare and medicine – has evolved rapidly in the course of the last years.⁷² D9.1 and D9.2 documented the evolution of the legal framework, from the Ethics Guidelines of Trustworthy AI⁷³, to the different EU policy documents issued between 2018 and 2024⁷⁴, to the most recent legislative proposals, including the AI Act. This section offers two main recommendations in the field of AI, as relevant to In Silico Trials researchers and end users. It suggests, first, to consider the ethical aspects entailed by the use of AI (section 4.1), and secondly, it suggests preparing for compliance with the forthcoming AI laws (section 4.2).⁷⁵

4.1. Reflect upon the ethical aspects entailed by the use of AI

The European Union has provided, in the last years guidance, for individuals involved in the use of AI, known as the High-Level Expert Group Ethics Guidelines on Trustworthy AI.⁷⁶ The guidelines proposed the respect of four ethical principles rooted in fundamental rights, which consist in the respect for human autonomy, the principle of prevention of harm, fairness and explicability.⁷⁷ Those principles were translated in seven key ethics requirements, summarised in the table below (Table 1).

⁷⁰ Marco Viceconti and others, ‘Introduction’ in Marco Viceconti and Luca Emili (eds), *Toward Good Simulation Practice* (Springer Nature Switzerland 2024) 4 <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-031-48284-7_1> accessed 28 March 2024.

⁷¹ It is not always the case, however. There are three main differentiations of AI-based in silico trials a non-AI based in silico trials. The first one consists of automated inferences over experimental data. The second one consists in AI methodologies used to predict quantities that are not measured experimentally. The third one concerns AI methodologies that support or replace human actions. For further disambiguation, see also Avicenna Alliance and VPHi Institute, ‘The Role of Artificial Intelligence within In Silico Medicine’ (2022) <<https://www.vph-institute.org/news/white-paper-the-role-of-artificial-intelligence-within-in-silico-medicine.html>>.

⁷² Elisabetta Biasin, ‘Comparative Worldwide Regulatory Approaches to AI’ (Joint Heads of Medicines Agencies (HMA)/European Medicines Agency (EMA) AI workshop – Smart regulation in a rapidly evolving world, Amsterdam, 20 November 2023) <<https://lirias.kuleuven.be/4123221&lang=en>>.

⁷³ High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, ‘Policy and Investment Recommendations for Trustworthy AI’ (2019).

⁷⁴ Including, for instance, the European Commission’s communication on Fostering a European Approach to Artificial Intelligence, the Commission’s White Paper on Artificial Intelligence, the European Parliament’s report on the Framework of ethical aspects of artificial intelligence, robotics and related technologies. For the full list, see D9.1 – Biasin, ‘In Silico World D9.1 Legal and Ethical Inventory’ (n 1) 37.

⁷⁵ Developing novel technologies, such as In Silico Trials tools may entail the consideration of moral aspects – as explained also further, see section 5 ‘Ethics’). In addition to bioethical considerations that are often necessary when performing research in the biomedical sphere, further consideration may be necessary when in silico tools entail the use of AI.

⁷⁶ High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, ‘Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI’.

⁷⁷ *ibid* 12.

HLEG Ethics requirements	
Human agency and oversight	AI systems should support human autonomy and decision making. Humans interacting with AI systems should be able to keep determination over themselves. This requirement implies the respect of fundamental rights of the individuals involved in the AI system’s processes and decision making, including their rights to privacy, data protection, dignity, health, non-discrimination. Fundamental rights impact assessment could help assess whether there could be negative impacts to fundamental rights. ⁷⁸
Technical robustness and safety	AI systems should be developed based on a preventative risk approach to mitigate risks of unintentional harm. They shall be developed in a way that they reliably perform as intended. It is crucial to consider security aspects in the development and use of AI systems, as well as accuracy-related aspects. ⁷⁹
Privacy and data governance	Privacy and data governance entail the due respect of privacy and data protection legal requirements, as well as the consideration of the quality and integrity of data. This is particularly important in terms of bias, inaccuracies, and other errors. ⁸⁰
Transparency	Transparency is closely linked to the principle of explicability and has implications regarding traceability, explainability and communication. Data sets and processes yielding the AI system’s decision should be documented to the best possible standard. An AI system's technical processes and related human decisions should be explainable. AI systems capabilities and limitations should be communicated to AI practitioners and end users as appropriate to the use case.
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness	AI systems should enable inclusion and diversity throughout their entire lifecycle. This ethics requirement includes the avoidance of unfair bias. AI tools should keep accessibility aspects and universal design principles in mind and where possible, stakeholder participation. ⁸¹
Societal and environmental well-being	As part of the principles of fairness and prevention of harm, AI systems should be developed and used with due regard to societal impacts. The societal effects of AI systems should be considered and monitored carefully. ⁸² The development, deployment, and user process of an AI system should consider sustainability values and environmental impact. ⁸³
Accountability	The ethical requirement of accountability requires that entities involved in developing and using AI systems have mechanisms in place to ensure responsibility and accountability for AI systems and their outcomes. The requirement includes the minimisation and reporting of negative impacts, as well as redress mechanisms for individuals and entities impacted by

⁷⁸ ibid 15.

⁷⁹ ibid 16.

⁸⁰ ibid 17.

⁸¹ ibid 18–19.

⁸² ibid 19.

⁸³ ibid.

	adverse impacts. Finally, AI systems (algorithms, data and design processes) should be auditable. ⁸⁴
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Table 1 HLEG Ethics principles

The ethics requirements above should not be considered as exhaustive – the HLEG guidelines suggest. They are formulated in such a broad manner to allow adaptive interpretation in a variety of cases. The HLEG guidelines can be read jointly with the AI HLEG Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (**ALTAI**) for self-assessment.⁸⁵ In the following part, we provide examples of how these ethics requirements could be translated into In Silico Trials.

- **Human agency and oversight:** In Silico Trials developers, while designing solutions, may consider carrying out a fundamental rights impact assessment and considering whether AI-based *in silico* solutions will have an impact on patient’s autonomy (potential questions in the assessment may include: to what extent the *in silico* tool may interfere with the patients’ autonomy or affect their decision-making processes concerning their health?).
- **Technical robustness and safety:** AI system providers should assess their ability to make correct predictions, recommendations or decisions based on data or models. Risks of inaccurate predictions and their possible impacts should be assessed, along with mitigating actions to correct unintended risks. Developers of *in silico* solutions should consider data quality when building datasets. In healthcare, having diverse datasets to avoid bias, errors, and inaccuracies is paramount.⁸⁶
- **Transparency:** it should be possible for patients to demand a suitable explanation of the decision process (e.g. a suggestion for specific treatment) provided by an AI-based *in silico* tool.⁸⁷
- **Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness:** datasets training or operation of *in silico* tools should reduce as many possible the risks of bias or incompleteness that could lead to unintended discrimination against certain patient population groups. As an additional measure, stakeholder participation from patients, healthcare professionals, and patient associations could be sought during the AI design and modelling.⁸⁸
- **Sustainability:** the entity in charge of the *in silico tool* development should assess the possible societal impacts of *in silico* solutions after their uptake (for example, their impact on patient trust in the healthcare system).
- **Accountability:** entities involved in the development and potential regulatory submission of AI-based *in silico* tools should consider the best ways to ensure that *in silico* algorithms, data and design processes can be transparently assessed by the relevant regulatory authorities.

⁸⁴ *ibid* 19–20.

⁸⁵ High Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, ‘Assessment List for Trustworthy AI’ (European Commission 2020) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>> accessed 28 August 2023.

⁸⁶ Elisabetta Biasin, ‘Healthcare AI: Overpromising and under-Representative? A Legal Perspective’ (*KU Leuven*, 5 September 2023) <<https://www.law.kuleuven.be/ai-summer-school/blogpost/Blogposts/AI-healthcare-underrepresentation>>.

⁸⁷ On transparency in AI-based healthcare, see also Carlo Combi and others, ‘A Manifesto on Explainability for Artificial Intelligence in Medicine’ (2022) 133 *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine* 102423; Anastasiya Kiseleva, Dimitris Kotzinos and Paul De Hert, ‘Transparency of AI in Healthcare as a Multilayered System of Accountabilities: Between Legal Requirements and Technical Limitations’ (2022) 5 *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence* 879603.

⁸⁸ For an example of stakeholder participation, see Ada Lovelace Institute, ‘Algorithmic Impact Assessment: A Case Study in Healthcare’ (2022) <<https://www.adalovelaceinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/02/Algorithmic-impact-assessment-a-case-study-in-healthcare.pdf>>.

In all the cases above, evaluations and decisions must be made in light of **multidisciplinary** perspectives. Finally, it is worthy of reporting that, in addition to the above principles, developers and end-users should be aware of other existing AI-related guidance provided by international organisations, such as the **World Health Organisation's** (WHO) Ethics and Governance of Artificial Intelligence and its Regulatory considerations on artificial intelligence for health.⁸⁹

4.2. Keep ready for upcoming AI legal requirements.

As already described in ISW D9.2, In Silico Trials solutions may, in some instances, fall under the definition of a **high-risk AI system**, and, therefore, the AI Act may be applicable. The requirements concerning artificial intelligence are at the moment of writing, in evolution. The **AI Act** reached a political agreement in December 2023 and in March 2024 passed the European Parliament.⁹⁰ Several versions of the text have been informally circulated among the different stakeholders. The final version is not available yet.⁹¹ However, given the existing proposals, it is possible to speculate on the **requirements** that users of In Silico Trials may want to consider for early compliance with the forthcoming AI Act.

The technology developers will have, first, to assess whether a In Silico Trials solution falls under the definition of a high-risk AI system. If they do, the AI Act requirements will become relevant for the providers of high-risk AI systems (i.e. the developers or those who put the systems on the market, if any modifications exist). The **AI Act requirements** for high-risk AI systems may concern, among the many, the adoption of a risk management system, ensuring data governance and data quality; taking due care of technical documentation and record-keeping duties; ensuring transparency and Information; human oversight; accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity.⁹²

5. Ethics

Ethical aspects are often involved in medicine and healthcare practice. The design, development and deployment of In Silico Trials tools implies, therefore, the consideration of **ethical aspects**. The section above has already tackled some aspects of AI ethics. However, it is also essential to consider the principles of biomedical ethics as applied to In Silico Trials context (section 5.1), responsible research aspects (section 5.2) and the most recent issues on the responsible use of Generative AI in scientific research (section 5.3).

5.1. Consider the principles of Biomedical Ethics

Before delving into the principles of Biomedical Ethics, it may be appropriate to clarify a possible preliminary question: **is there a difference between law and ethics?** Law and ethics might indeed appear similar to persons approaching them for the first time. They both offer rules by which humans are expected to behave in society. Nevertheless, **they are different**. Laws formally establish enforceable rules and standards within a given legal system. Ethics is a branch of philosophy reflecting human values, principles and purposes. It

⁸⁹ World Health Organisation, 'Ethics and Governance of AI for Health: WHO Guidance' <<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240029200>> accessed 28 August 2023; World Health Organisation, 'Regulatory Considerations on Artificial Intelligence for Health' <<https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/373421/9789240078871-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>>.

⁹⁰ Luca Bertuzzi, 'EU Countries Give Crucial Nod to First-of-a-Kind Artificial Intelligence Law' (*www.euractiv.com*, 2 February 2024) <<https://www.euractiv.com/section/artificial-intelligence/news/eu-countries-give-crucial-nod-to-first-of-a-kind-artificial-intelligence-law/>> accessed 5 February 2024.

⁹¹ The latest version (at the time of reviewing the deliverable before submission) is available at this link: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2024-0138-FNL-COR01_EN.pdf.

⁹² For a punctual analysis of these requirements, see D9.1 and D9.2.

concerns reflections over the behaviour of individuals within society from a moral perspective.⁹³ Laws are often based on ethical issues – let us think of the history of informed consent requirements, which originated in light of the post-Second World War ethical debates.⁹⁴ However, sometimes laws are not enough and, in some cases, they may fall short in driving researchers' and healthcare professionals' decision-making.

In many circumstances – as an example, complex medical procedures – ethics may serve as a driver for what is formally prescribed by the law.⁹⁵ In other circumstances, ethics plays a role when the speed of technological innovations goes faster than lawmaking processes. Similarly to what happened in the past, the uptake of many technologies or health issues has required public moral scrutiny – let us think of reproductive technologies (such as in vitro fertilisation), end-of-life decision-making, organ transplantation. The same can be suggested in the context of novel medical device and medical product testing approaches. In Silico Trials may entail novel problems worthy of scrutiny from an ethical perspective.

Starting from these premises, in the In Silico World project the partners were suggested to consider a set of ethical principles, namely the framework provided by Beauchamp and Childress (“**Principles of Biomedical Ethics**”).⁹⁶ These principles, historically meant to be used for practical healthcare decision-making, are commonly used ethical approaches in healthcare and biomedical science. This report suggests not only In Silico World partners but future In Silico Trials researchers and end users to consider these moral principles from the inception, development, and deployment (more generally, the full lifecycle of *in silico* tools) as well as its relevant research processes. We recapitulate in the following lines the main aspects of the biomedical ethics principles.

The moral principles of biomedical ethics are four: autonomy, beneficence, non-maleficence, and justice. The principle of **autonomy** consists of a negative obligation not to interfere in a patient's choice and the positive obligation to provide appropriate information to make informed decisions.⁹⁷ The principle of **non-maleficence**, implies the obligation not to harm other persons. It is often associated with the Hippocratic Oath, or the “do no harm” obligation, requiring not to inflict evil or harm nor impose risks of harm to patients. The principle of **beneficence** requires contributing to the patients' welfare. Examples of rules supported by the principle of beneficence include helping persons with disabilities, preventing harm from occurring to others, and removing conditions that will cause harm to others.⁹⁸ Finally, the principle of **justice** highlights fairness and equality among individuals. It advocates for a fair distribution of goods within society and implies the generating of the most significant benefits for lower advantaged members. Applying this principle also includes guaranteeing protection against stigmatisation or unjust discrimination towards individuals.

Former In Silico World reports described in detail the theoretical background of the biomedical ethics principles and offered specific examples to In Silico Trials research. The figure below recapitulates the examples provided in the former reports, to which we refer for further details.⁹⁹

⁹³ For a more in-depth discussion on the difference between law and ethics and how they interplay with each other see Anton Vedder, ‘Mind the Gap. Managing the Expectations of Legal Scholars Turning to Ethics for Help Where the Law Does Not yet Provide Answers’, *Rethinking IT and IP Law. Celebrating 30 Years CITIP* (Intersentia; Cambridge, Antwerp, Chicago 2019).

⁹⁴ J Vollmann and R Winau, ‘Informed Consent in Human Experimentation before the Nuremberg Code’ (1996) 313 *BMJ* 1445.

⁹⁵ This paragraph summarises and simplifies the discussions in ISW D9.1 and D9.2, see both reports respectively for a more- in-depth analysis.

⁹⁶ Tom L Beauchamp and James F Childress, *Principles of Biomedical Ethics* (5th ed., New York: Oxford university press 2001).

⁹⁷ Privacy and informed consent are examples of this principle in healthcare and biomedical research.

⁹⁸ Beauchamp and Childress (n 96) 167.

⁹⁹ See Biasin, Elisabetta (n 1) 48–53.

Figure 2 Examples of biomedical ethics principles applied in the context of In Silico Trials (as detailed in D9.2)

5.2. Perform responsible research

Performing, and continuously working towards responsible innovation is a crucial element for in Silico Trials developers. A useful compass is Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), a science policy approach and guiding principle for research and innovation, promoted by the European Commission. It is based on the understanding that present modes of innovating with science and technology fail because they insufficiently take into account societal needs and values.¹⁰⁰ Science and technology, and the individuals propelling its advancements, serve as the driving forces behind the most transformative discoveries that have shaped the world we live in. Yet, alongside positive societal changes benefiting the well-being of individuals, innovations have also frequently introduced novel risks and implications. Societal impacts and ethical considerations are often side-lined during the innovation developments, receiving attention only as an afterthought. RRI thus calls on all stakeholders to work together to align research and innovation with the values, needs, and expectations of society in an anticipatory manner. Acting on this imperative, in Silico Trials developers should strive towards not merely assuming a *shared* responsibility but also actively embodying responsibility within their daily activities and proactively seeking strategies to contribute to responsible innovation and society.¹⁰¹

5.3. Use Generative AI responsibly

In addition to the above requirements, researchers involved in In Silico Trials research are likely to use Generative AI. Generative AI could be used for different purposes in scientific research and medicine. It could be used in medical settings for diagnosis and clinical care, patient-guide use, clinical and administrative tasks, medical and nursing education, and scientific research.¹⁰² In **scientific research**, Generative AI could be used for various tasks, from content creation to writing scientific articles, as conversational agents, and beyond.¹⁰³ Generative AI could also be used to **create synthetic data** for data collection in In Silico Trials.

¹⁰⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Options for strengthening responsible research and innovation: report of the Expert Group on the State of Art in Europe on Responsible Research and Innovation, Publications Office, 2013, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/46253>.

¹⁰¹ Work Package 5 of the In Silico World project is currently working on an Ethical Manifesto laying out the social and ethical responsibilities of the in silico community. It will serve as a compass for in Silico Trials developers and demonstrates the in silico community's commitment to responsible innovation.

¹⁰² World Health Organisation, 'Ethics and Governance of Artificial Intelligence for Health. Guidance on Large Multi-Modal Models' <<https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/375579/9789240084759-eng.pdf?sequence=1>>.

¹⁰³ Tirth Dave, Sai Anirudh Athaluri and Satyam Singh, 'ChatGPT in Medicine: An Overview of Its Applications, Advantages, Limitations, Future Prospects, and Ethical Considerations' (2023) 6 Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence 1169595.

This section suggests below some main points to responsibly reflect upon while using Generative AI in scientific and In Silico Trials research.

- **Confidentiality:** researchers and engineers using generative AI within the context of In Silico Trials research should be aware of data confidentiality in general and medical confidentiality obligations in healthcare. This is particularly important when inputting data to Generative AI tools. Researchers should be aware that providing data to specific Generative AI tools may entail further processing (potentially, even unlawfully) by the same companies.¹⁰⁴
- **Cross-check and validation:** results provided by Generative AI need to be cross-checked. As demonstrated by several studies, Generative AI results can be factually inaccurate.¹⁰⁵ However, in scientific research, it remains essential to maintain scientific rigor and, therefore, scrutinize – to the extent possible – the results provided by Generative AI before using them for research and publications.¹⁰⁶
- **Bias, complexity and scientific argumentation:** Throughout the last few years, several strands of AI literature have underlined the perils of AI biases.¹⁰⁷ The same eventuality applies to Generative AI, whose results could be biased, too.¹⁰⁸ Researchers making use of Generative AI tools should consider this aspect carefully, e.g. when generating synthetic data. Bias could also be shown in other uses of Generative AI, such as when used as a conversationalist agent. There, for example, it might suggest only majoritarian arguments while leaving other argumentations aside. Scientific argumentation is nevertheless based on, to the greatest extent possible, a full spectrum of argumentations, and therefore, researchers should be aware of this aspect.
- **Authorship, copyright, transparency and credit:** since the general uptake of Generative AI tools by the broader public, intellectual property protection concerns have arisen.¹⁰⁹ Generative AI tools may entail using copyrighted information, and therefore, specific input data could be restricted in licensing. When researchers use Generative AI, intellectual property aspects should not be left aside. In some instances, the use of Generative AI should be disclosed – for example, in the context of specific journal submissions.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable aimed to offer user-friendly guidance with **twelve “golden rules” addressed to researchers and end users** on the ethical and legal requirements applicable to In Silico Trials. The deliverable focused,

¹⁰⁴ See the case on ChatGpt Italian DPA (March 2023): Garante per la Protezione dei Dati Personali, ‘Provvedimento Dell’11 Aprile 2023 [9874702]’ (11 April 2023) <<https://www.gdpd.it/web/guest/home/docweb/-/docweb-display/docweb/9874702>> accessed 27 May 2023.

¹⁰⁵ On factual accuracy of generative AI, see the ‘Op-ED: “ChatGPT. Time to Think of Accuracy as a Legal Requirement (For Real)” by Elisabetta Biasin’ (*EU Law Live*, 24 April 2023) <<https://eulawlive.com/op-ed-chatgpt-time-to-think-of-accuracy-as-a-legal-requirement-for-real-by-elisabetta-biasin/>> accessed 10 May 2023.

¹⁰⁶ Example of unethical use of Generative AI in scientific writing, happened in a renown journal: Jordan Pearson, ‘Study Featuring AI-Generated Giant Rat Penis Retracted, Journal Apologizes’ (*Vice News*, 16 February 2023) <<https://www.vice.com/en/article/4a389b/ai-midjourney-rat-penis-study-retracted-frontiers>> accessed 22 February 2024.

¹⁰⁷ Emilio Ferrara, ‘Fairness and Bias in Artificial Intelligence: A Brief Survey of Sources, Impacts, and Mitigation Strategies’ (2023) 6 *Sci 3*.

¹⁰⁸ I Glenn Cohen, ‘What Should ChatGPT Mean for Bioethics?’ (2023) 23 *The American Journal of Bioethics* 8.

¹⁰⁹ See the case brought by the New York Times versus OpenAI. Sarah Taffe-Maguire, ‘The New York Times Sues OpenAI and Microsoft over Copyright Infringement’ (*Sky News*, 28 December 2023) <<https://news.sky.com/story/the-new-york-times-sues-openai-and-microsoft-over-copyright-infringement-13038277>> accessed 22 February 2024.

following the analyses carried out in D9.1 and D9.2, on the following areas of legislation: privacy, data protection and governance, medical devices and medicinal products, and artificial intelligence. Further to the legal requirements, the report included a section with perspectives from an ethical standpoint. Ultimately, these “golden rules” may help researchers and end users navigate the complex legal and ethical scenarios surrounding the innovative – yet still uncertain – In Silico Trials regulatory domain.

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